

ISic1172

I.Sicily inscription 1172

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Cephaloedium

Place of origin (modern)

Cefalù

Provenance

Countryside inland

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8812

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θεοῖς καταχθ
2. ονίοις θά
3. λλος ἔζη
4. σε ἔτη ε
5. Χαιρέτω ὁ ἀναγν
6. ούς

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284918

EDR 112786

EDCS 39102326

PHI 140655

PHI 175604

Bibliography

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